

An Instinctual Analysis of Literature

Dr. Aparna Sharma

Assistant Professor, AIESR, Amity University, Noida, U.P., India

ABSTRACT

Literature is the mirror of society, is a very well said quote. In every era the need of literature is felt. We can say that literature is the food to soul. The paper will be focusing on that how literature can change our perception and how it can motivate us to live a life of virtues. The emotions and morality could be taught in an indirect method by the study of literature. In today's scenario when materialism is the prime focus youngsters are losing the ethics of life, if literature departments will be abolished then the aroma of nature will not be there, and the society will be a place of dry concrete only.

The article will be focusing on that, the technical academics alone cannot fulfill the need of hour; we need good human beings for a good and prosperous society. The perspectives given by the writers help the people to become sensitive, moral and courageous for prosperity in life. It is an inseparable part of life; it should be nurtured instead of curtailing its domains. Literature must be read beyond academics, it must be read between the lines.

Key words- literature, society.

Paper:

“Literature adds to reality, it does not simply describe it. It enriches the necessary competencies that daily life requires and provides; and in this respect, it irrigates the deserts that our lives have already become.” – C.S.Lewis.

The famous minute written by Macaulay on Indian education in 1935 was dictated by an educational, indeed, a literary aim.¹ Macaulayan syllabus, claimed that only great and serious literature should be taught and not the language. The standard canon of English literature from Chaucer and Shakespeare, Milton, Dryden, Pope, Wordsworth, Coleridge, Shelley to Browning was read in original for its elevating and enlightening functions.²

The concrete and strong ground on which we are standing today is the gift of that era in which the knowledge is shared through fairy tales and stories. One of the great features of life today is the curious shrinkage of the world. The invention of various modes of conveyance and communication like air services and internet, have helped to annihilate space. Of their scientific importance and social value there is no need to speak here; but the cumulative effect of these things upon the psychology of the day is worth noting, in as much as it reacts upon our literature.³ The primitive as well as the contemporary literature make us grow as balanced personality because it imparts us vision to think logically. ‘Literature is the mirror of society’, true, and we are developing by tracing out flaws and rectifying them through that mirror.

An individual's persona consists of perfect balance of mind and heart. Mechanic era of today only requires professional dealing everywhere without sentiments. If the literature departments be abolished, we will soon be reaching to a total dry atmosphere, where the people will be involved in rat race of cutthroat competition. A place where language is needed for buttering, for pomp and show and for imitation only. In one instance one may find this world very attractive and lucrative but the truth is that it is shallow from inside, everybody then will be leading towards a life which is a reel life & people may long for the real one.

I wish that the people dealing with literature of various languages should come in front to tell the world that science, philosophy, history, fiction etc. all are there because fiction was there in name of literature. Fiction prompted people to work on the imaginative aspect which resulted in innumerable innovations of various fields. They should give a clarion call in defense of literature.

A fable may not be doing any good to a child but imprinting secretly on his latent mind the art of imagination. A literary work in majority makes the reader feel that the story line is quite near to his own or to the one staying next door. A feeling

of closeness to the story makes an impact on mind and one comes up either with suggestions or follows the track paved by the writer.

If we search we may find that in some form or the other literature is there in our life. The initial phase of life when a child is not at all receptive to maximum things even then lullabies sung for him (a type of oral literature) are able to make him calm. His gestures reveal that he is trying to decipher the meaning. This is an example that literature is there in the very basic lessons of life, irrespective of the caste or the status of the family. So there seems no point in abolishing of the literary departments. Today the people think that what is the need of literature? They forget that the editorials of magazines and papers are the works of literature. Movies, plays, serials, songs all are the extended version of literature itself. What more to say all proverbs and which are having the capacity to make a tremendous change to life are the parts of famous literary works.

Today the market for literary English and literature-based courses is fast dwindling, paving way for Spoken English, Written English, Business English, Management English, English for IT, Technical writing, Communication Skills⁴ etc. which are in great demand today. If the literary departments will be closed and the knowledge of language only will be imparted, we will only be producing machines and not the combination of mechanic intellect and humanitarian approach. No doubt that the mentioned forms of English is essential to cope up with the demands of professional competition of today, but one needs a vision also to produce the best out of that knowledge. That vision comes from the study of literature only.

Good books rather good literature always remains in demand. People wish to relish the cup of morning tea with newspaper, which is, if not a literature in true sense at least a part of it. Excellence in language can fetch one a good job, to earn luxuries for his family but then what will satisfy the inner hunger of soul? Only literature can. The number of advises we are getting from our elders are an oral version of the written literature, as all persuasive writings are having some literature as base, which gives an understanding of life, provides courage to face the challenges of life.

Abolishing literature departments is like hindering the scope for all type of progress of human race. The works of literature holds our history, our culture, our tradition, and moreover binds us with our past as well as with future. It deals with the universal problems⁵ and their solutions as well.

Maxim Gorky's, Mother is an example of the statement; it is portraying the conditions of the people involved and the atrocities of the common masses on the other hand. This novel must had given a lot of impetus to their contemporary struggle during Russian Revolution. On the same footage Indian struggle for independence was also marked with the contribution of many literary works in name of newspapers, magazines, novels etc. in absence of which we would have not been able to flourish the idea of freedom amongst the contemporary masses.

Even if one is talking purely in terms of science a deep study can confer the presence of literature at its base, though concerned with the subject only. The idea is that we have to ponder over the base of any innovation of any field, what is that? Is it not the searching of new avenues within the fold of the old researches? One can find the renowned philosophers, scientists, academicians of technical fields, judges, lawyers, financial experts, and managers are producing good literature. They supply the food which develops a strong clear, original life of the mind; which makes the imagination active and creative; which feeds the young spirit with the deeds and images of heroes; which set the real in true relations to the ideal.⁶ This is like a chain,

Good literature, better understanding, new ideas, researches, new theories evolved, personal experiences, framed in literature (experiences, autobiographies), good literature.

Though there is nothing in name of good or bad literature, literature is literature. But in norms of Indian ideology we are specific about judging between right and wrong according to the set prevailing norms of the society. The literary departments are just reading between the lines for the motivation of their students. In pure form of fiction also, the idea behind every plot is coming from the mind and heart which receives all the concepts from the society only. Shakespeare opened our eyes to a whole new world, peopled by the creatures of his own mind; and once we have encountered them, they seem often far more real and solid,⁷ his plays depict the contemporary emotions, styles, practices of the people. Canterbury Tales gives a varied picture of all the minds of different profession and age group. Tagore from India's diverse religious traditions drew many ideas, both from ancient text and popular poetry⁸

These types of works go parallel with the positive traits and flaws of the characters, through plot, they inspire the readers to go for the right path, which consists of maximum human values like honesty, dedication, truthfulness, etc. As a result, these works are responsible for producing good human beings who can stand with others during their need of hour and proving themselves the best wherever they are working.

Literature can be compared to an Ayurvedic prescription for the betterment of an individual. It cures from within turns one into a purified soul. It is not that one has to go through spiritual literature but even a simple small poem like Daffodils⁹ by Wordsworth or Success/Hope¹⁰ by Emily Dickinson, can get one connected with the natural aspect of Almighty and can reform one's individuality. It latently works for the enhancement of values in life.

Today's era requires perfect balanced personalities which literature can give. Go through the life history of any successful man and you will encounter the fact that in their young age they were introduced to good works of literature. Great literature, however, as Mr. Shaw knows perfectly well, is great only so far as it is a living organic thing, intimately related to life and related in two ways. Its tap-root lies in the soil from which it draws its sustenance; the soil of a particular age with its limitations and characteristics; but its flower is blown upon by the breezes of heaven and fed by the rain and the sun – in this respect it is related to the universal and is an expression not of an age but of ages.¹¹

Now a question can come that what contribution a pessimistic and bad literature can make to a person's life? Indian ideology reveals that maximum of us are taught to judge the right and wrong from our childhood days. If one is able to judge that the work is of below standard or inculcating the negativity to mind; many will take the lesson not to get involved in the practices narrated in that literature. Pessimistic Shelly guides us not to become too emotional, as life is to go in all the odd situations. On the other hand, write-ups of Khushwant Singh can persuade us not to go for farce.

The people, who are good, are courageous too. Literature makes one good and results in various acts even beyond capacity. Simply look into the deepness of the lines narrated by Tagore,
"Who will take my work, asks the setting sun.
None has the answer in the whole silent world.
The earthen lamp says humbly from a corner.
I will, my lord, as best as I can."¹²

It provides society with guiding principles of life. If these are not taught and plain language studies will be there, will we not be missing the emotional content from life? Electricity is having its own utility but why before every occasion traditional lamp is lighted? Because it is the base of all warmth life is having. In the same manner literature is like the foundation stones of a building, we might not be able to see them, but they are there. We can ignore them for an instance but cannot remove them. Literature has always served as an authentic source of information from all around the world. Major works of history, philosophy, science, etc. marked with the influence of literature. It serves as an enormous information base. Research works by famous inventors and literary works by notable scientists often narrate stories of their groundbreaking discoveries and inferences.¹³

Literature consists of the norms and rules and regulations of an idealistic society. People generally connect themselves with the characters and try to follow the idealistic track of their footprints. Human tendency is to get the appreciation and praise for each and every act of them. Literary works guide and persuade them for logical thinking about do's and don'ts which help them to come up as rational being liked by all. No scientific work can provide this service. Government now a days is working on the issues of value education through aesthetic education whereby people can learn to have the capacity to be moved by works of art, literature or music.¹⁴

Who can ignore, "a perfect man is like a lotus - leaf in the water or like a mud - fish in the marsh"? Neither of them is polluted by the element in which it lives.¹⁵ This comparison is only possible in literature, think who will decipher between the lines if literary departments be closed?

Literature brings us closer to God which indirectly purifies our soul and makes us the perfect being. The idea of direct, joyful, and totally fearless relationship with God can be found in many of Tagore's religious writings; including the poems of Gitanjali.¹⁶ Not only this but it can serve as a tool to combat communalism prevailing in the air of today. Tagore's devotional poems makes them appeal to readers irrespective of their beliefs,¹⁷ the ones in particular which combine images of human love and devotion.

Every era has some needs and demands of its period. As all the fields observe change in their style and presentation so is the need of literature. Instead of eliminating it from the scene we can go for some innovative techniques of explanation; rather it can serve the purpose of interdisciplinary perspective. Literature as we have seen throughout its history, needs from time to time to be reinforced with fresh vitality, with new vigor; otherwise it will languish and decay.¹⁸

The literature of tomorrow lies in the womb of today, every action, every attitude of ours today, is helping to mold the nature and destiny of these unborn child.¹⁹ One should look for opportunities to showcase the power of literature, how it can evoke emotion, draw a reader into a scenario or persuade a person to change an opinion on a topic. What more to say, literature can act as.

- A mirror to enable readers to reflect on life problems and circumstances
- A source of knowledge
- A source of ideological challenge
- A means to peer into the past, and the future
- A means to reflect on inner struggles
- An introduction to the realities of life and death
- A vehicle for raising and discussion of social issues²⁰

Great literature is still important today. The value of reading should not be ignored even when new technologies seem to dominate our lives. Biographies inspire us to rise above our own challenges while philosophies preserved in books help us to see beyond our known boundaries. An imaginary world can give perspective by allowing us to step back and view problems in another setting. If these treasures are cast aside or replaced, our society will certainly suffer from its loss.²¹

What more to say, do you think that emotions could be felt through scientific and language subjects? True that they are there inside every human being but then who will polish them if there will be no literature teachings. It works as a sensitizing agent for heart and mind; it's like the real experience of the hardships and pleasures of life. Literature awakens, enlarges, enhances and refines our humanity in a way that almost nothing else can.²² May be it appears as if a hyperbolic statement; but the truth is that literature gives us a style of living with all warmth of life and if it will be missing then a time will come when our world of humans be better be called as the world of Robots.

This is the high time, we need to ponder over the words of American writer James Allen, "You are today where your thoughts have brought you, and you will be tomorrow where your thoughts take you. You cannot escape the result of your thoughts".²³ By closing literary departments we will be closing the door to a balanced life. They need to be modified to meet the demands of the age, instead of thinking about their closure, we should think for their reincarnation.

Phases of progress are known to be given by literary teachings only as the humans learn from stories.²⁴ All other works of science, finance, geography, computers etc. are there to result in knowledge and physical comfort; aesthetic parameter is not a part of it. On the other hand literature inculcates a perception of sensitivity, motivation and creativity. In fine we have a long way to go; in the concrete of materialism literature is like the wide shade, one should think to go with it and not without it. In the words of Frost,

"Woods are lovely dark and deep, I have promises to keep.
Miles to go before I sleep, miles to go before I sleep."²⁵

FOOTNOTES / REFERENCES

- [1] Krishnaswamy N & Krishnaswamy Lalitha, *The Story of English Language in India*, Foundation Books, New Delhi, 2006, p-39 ibid, p-127
- [2] Rikett Arthur Comton, *A History of English Literature*, USB Pub. & Dis. Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 2006, p- 659
- [3] Krishnaswamy N & Krishnaswamy Lalitha, *The Story of English Language in India*, Foundation Books, New Delhi, 2006, p-181,
- [4] Rikett Arthur Comton, *A History of English Literature* USB Pub. & Dis. Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 2006, p- 664 Source; Internet
- [5] Quennell Peter & Johnson Hamish, *Who's Who in Shakespeare*, Routledge, London, preface-viii Sen Amartya, *The Argumentative Indians*, Penguin Books, London, 2005, p- 96
- [6] Wordsworth William, *Poems in two Volumes*, Vol.1, Longman, London, 1807.
- [7] Dickinson Emily, *The Collected Poems of Emily Dickinson*, Barnes & Noble Books, New York, 2003, p – 6 & 22

- [8] Rikett Arthur Comton, *A History of English Literature*, USB Pub. & Dis. Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 2006, p- 664
- [9] Tagore Rabindranath, *Ref;Competition Science Vision*,Mar2000, p-5 Oak Manali, *Importance of Literature*, on Internet.
- [10] Aspin N. David & Chapman D.Judith, *Value Education and Lifelong Learning*, Springer, The Netherlands, 2007, p-22
- [11] Muller Max, Ramkrishna, *His Life and Sayings*, p- 112Sen Amartya ,*The Argumentative Indians*, Penguin Books, London,2005, p-96
- [12] Radice William, *Rabindranath Tagore; Selected Short Stories*, Harmonds worth; Penguin, 1991, p – 28
- [13] Rikett Arthur Comton, *A History of English Literature*, USB Pub. & Dis. Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi,2006, p – 659Ibid, p – 680
- [14] Cairney Trevor H., *Pathways to Literacy*, Cassell, London, 1995, p – 77,78.
- [15] Timson Levi, *The Relevance of Literature*, source; Internet
- [16] Gioia Diana, *Importance of Reading*, The Commonwealth June 2006, in National Endowments for the Arts, p – 19
- [17] Giardina Ric, *Living a Balanced Life*, Infinity Books, New Delhi, 2005, p-29
- [18] Aspin N. David & Chapman D. Judith (Editors), *Value Education and Lifelong Learning*, Springer, The Netherlands, 2007, p-140
- [19] Frost Robert "*Stopping by Woods on a Snowy Evening*" is a poem written in 1922, published in 1923 in his New Hampshire volume